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MODERNIZATION OF THE SUB-COMPLEX OF DESERT PASTURE LIVESTOCK AND OPTIMIZATION OF ITS ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

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Abstract: The article is based on the need to modernize production and services and optimize them using innovative technologies, regardless of the form of management, as well as the fact that deep processing of raw materials in the regions is a great resource for improving the socio-economic efficiency of the subsystem.

Keywords: management system, infrastructure, optimization, modernization, innovation, desert-pastoral complex, service, processing, efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Desert pasture regions of the republic Desert - pastoral animal husbandry, in particular, specializes in the breeding of karakul sheep, intensive use of natural resources of desert areas, development of productive forces in remote areas, increasing the efficiency of agro-industrial complex and on this basis to address socio-economic development.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The studied literature shows the current state of processing, infrastructure and its development, service and improvement of the system of processing of desert livestock products, optimization of the organizational and structural component of the desert-pasture livestock complex, the interaction between desert farms and service enterprises. devoted to issues such as improving economic relations [1,2,3,4,5].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the research was formed as a result of the study of theoretical and practical information, legislation and other legal documents, literary sources and publications. The study was based on the links between theory

and practice, but also used economic and statistical analysis, comparison, scientific forecasting and other methods.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The importance of the desert - pasture livestock complex in the national economy is determined by the products produced in the industry. An important feature of desert-pastoral animal husbandry is its development at the expense of cheap natural pasture fodder. Desert - pastoral animal husbandry is characterized by the production of highly valuable raw materials for industry such as astrakhan leather, sheep, goat and camel wool, sheep and other livestock skins, delicious sheep and other livestock meat, medicinal camel and sheep milk is a unique field of animal husbandry.

Ensuring sustainable economic and social development of the agro-industrial complex in a market economy is the production of a scientifically based management system of direct agriculture and its introduction in farms, districts and regions. The central part of this system is the modernization of pastures for desert - pastoral areas and the organization of production on the basis of intensive technologies and their processing on the ground. An important issue in this process is to determine the optimal production composition of the sub-complex of desert - pasture livestock, the formation of the economic mechanism and its functioning.

The size of karakul farms and their production units includes the form of management, location of settlements in the area, the state of production and social infrastructure, agricultural land, number of sheep and other livestock, number of workers, level of specialization of the farm, direction of production, ie breeding farms, breeding farms (reproduktory) farms, commercial farms, the availability of natural pastures and pasture rotation, the level of application of feeding and storage technology, the state of water supply, etc.

The balance of the above factors ensures the optimality of economic and production units, among which the decisive factor is the provision of food.

Due to the continuous and fragmented use of pastures, the lack of phytomeliorative measures to increase their productivity, most pastures are currently in crisis at different levels. According to data obtained in recent years, 9 mln. As a result of plant deflation per hectare, the yield increased by 20% to 5 mln. ha in pastures by 20-30% and 2.5 mln. per hectare in pastures decreased by 40% and above. The main factor causing the pasture crisis is overfeeding. In addition, human activities such as the use of pasture vegetation as firewood, man-made factors, development of mineral resources, laying of main pipelines also have a significant negative impact on desert-pasture ecosystems.

However, due to the degradation of most of the desert pastures, declining productivity of natural pastures and insufficient water supply, increasing livestock numbers, karakul sheep receive only 50-55% instead of at least 85.0% in natural pastures It is expedient to establish desert-pastoral livestock complexes on the basis of modernization of pastures in order to radically increase the efficiency of services and to organize the processing of crops .

The results of the study of the activities of desert-pastoral farms showed that the number of sheep in the herds on specialized farms does not exceed 500-600 heads instead of 750, or 20-33% lower than the established norms. More than 60 percent of farms have up to 50 sheep, 18-20 percent up to 100 heads, 7 percent up to 200 heads, 5 percent up to 300 heads and 3 percent 500 or more sheep. The size of farms also varies by sheep head, with only 8-10 percent of farmers with 1,000 or more heads. The small size of herds and farms in terms of the number of sheep is one of the main factors limiting the increase in production efficiency. Therefore, it is expedient to optimize the primary production units (herds) in specialized farms, the sizes of farms and dehkan farms, with the effective use of new technologies.

To feed 500 head of sheep 1500 ra. natural pastures are required. Introducing innovative technology of pasture use in these areas, ie 0.28-0.29 ha per head of sheep. economic development of desert areas through the development of production

infrastructure and the formation of processing of products, along with the creation of high-yield artificial pastures, which will increase the number of sheep to 2,500 heads on primary farms and 300-500 heads on farms, and dramatically increase production efficiency. - serves as an important source of funding for social development.

Construction of modern housing, production and service buildings and structures for shepherds' houses and service personnel for the organization of desert-pastoral livestock complexes. At the same time, it is expedient to determine the number of service outlets for production, given that the bulk of karakul sheep are reared on small farms, as well as taking into account the capacity of existing equipment and technologies. One zoo-veterinary outlet in the area with 8000-12000 head of sheep, one fixed or portable artificial insemination point for every 3500-4000 head of ewes, lambing and shearing points in the area of 10000-12000 head of ewes, 700-800 heads It is necessary to establish a milking parlor with 5 milking machines per sheep, one meat and sheep skin processing enterprise in the area with 54.0-55.0 thousand sheep.

The table shows the number of production service outlets in Navoi region and Karakul district, based on the characteristics of the location of desert and pasture livestock and the availability of available technologies. Its creation will lead to the creation of new jobs.

Table 1 .

Demand for outlets of livestock services in Navoi region						
Indicators	Navoi region	Districts				
		Konimekh	Kiziltepa	Nurata	Tomdi	Uchkuduk
Zooveterinary point:						
conditional sheep number, thousand head	2721.9	495.3	402.3	418.0	332.1	142.9
service standard, general	10,000	10,000	12000	10,000	8000	8000
number of points required, pcs	272	50	33	42	41	18

Artificial escape point:						
number of ewes, thousand heads	1046.6	267.7	102.8	205.2	162.9	64.9
service standard, general	4000	3500	4000	4000	3500	3500
number of points required, pcs	262	76	26	51	46	18
Lamb slaughter point:						
number of lambs to be slaughtered, thousand head	494.9	132.4	43.4	92.4	89.3	38.4
service standard, general	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000
number of points required, pcs	99	26	9	18	18	8
Sheep shearing point:						
number of sheep, thousand head	1869.0	453.7	166.9	350.7	316.4	125.7
service standard, general	12000	12000	12000	12000	12000	12000
number of points required, pcs	156	38	14	29	26	10
Sheep milking area:						
marrie mother sheep number, thousand head	494.9	132.4	43.4	92.4	89.3	38.4
service standard, general	800	800	800	800	800	800
number of points required, pcs	618	165	54	12	11	5

Source: Developed based on the author's research.

For example, 1360-1370 jobs will be created in Navoi region due to veterinary stations. 785-790 people will be employed for a month in the organization of artificial insemination of ewes, 1180-1190 people will be employed for 30-35 days in the slaughterhouses of karakul lambs, 1870-1875 people will be sheared for 2-3 months during which 7415-7420 people will be able to be involved in milking marri sheep.

One of the reasons for the backwardness of the socio-economic development of desert-pastoral areas is the fact that the products grown are delivered to consumers in the form of raw materials.

The analysis shows that the purchase price of one piece of astrakhan skin is 38.0 thousand soums, it is 118.0 thousand soums as a finished product, 1ts of meat, 1ts of wool, one sheepskin is 2000.0 and 2780.0, respectively; 800.0 and 3478.6;

15.0 and 225.0 thousand soums, or processed products were sold at prices 3-4 times higher.

The results of the study show that processing enterprises absorb 80.0-90.0% of the profits, despite the fact that 70.0-75.0% of production costs fall on the share of raw materials. This is due to the fact that the purchased unit of raw materials in the form of finished products is sold at prices 3.0-4.0 times higher. One of the important ways to eliminate inconsistencies between producers and processors of raw materials is to organize their processing on the basis of integration and cooperation in areas where livestock products are produced.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the results of research:

1. Establishment of desert-pasture livestock complexes on the basis of pasture modernization;
2. Introduce innovative technology of use in pastures, ie 0.28-0.29 ha per sheep. to create high-yield artificial pastures and increase the number of sheep in the primary production units of specialized farms and farms to 2,500 heads and in farms to 300-500 heads;
3. One zoo-veterinary outlet in the area with 8000-12000 head of sheep, one fixed or portable artificial insemination point for every 3500-4000 head of ewes, lamb slaughtering and shearing points in the area of every 10000-12000 head of sheep, 700- Establishment of a milking parlor consisting of 5 milking machines for 800 head of sheep, one meat and sheep skin processing enterprise in the area with 54.0-55.0 thousand sheep;
4. One of the important ways to eliminate inconsistencies between producers and processors of raw materials is to organize their processing on the basis of integration and cooperation in areas where livestock products are produced;

5. We propose to eliminate the problem of unemployment by creating new jobs through the organization of services and processing of raw materials in the regions.

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